

Examining the Relationship Between Leisure Management and Digital Addiction Levels in Tennis Athletes

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Research Article

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between leisure management and digital addiction among tennis athletes. A total of 219 participants were included, comprising 53% females and 47% males, with the majority aged between 18–23 years. Regarding athletic experience, 54.8% had 0–3 years, and 27.4% had 8 years or more. Most participants primarily used smartphones (74.4%), with Twitter being the most frequently used social media platform (78.1%). Normality analyses indicated that both leisure management and digital addiction scores were approximately normally distributed (leisure: skewness = 0.246, kurtosis = 0.526; digital addiction: skewness = -0.005, kurtosis = -0.525). Independent samples t-tests revealed no significant differences between genders in leisure management or digital addiction ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, ANOVA results showed no significant differences in leisure management or digital addiction across age groups or athletic experience ($p > 0.05$). Social media platform usage also did not significantly affect leisure management ($p = 0.782$), though Instagram users exhibited slightly higher digital addiction scores, approaching significance ($p = 0.065$). Pearson correlation analysis indicated a weak but significant negative relationship between leisure management and digital addiction ($r = -0.164$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that athletes who manage their leisure time more effectively tend to have slightly lower levels of digital addiction. These findings highlight the importance of structured leisure activities in mitigating digital dependency among athletes, emphasizing the potential benefits of targeted interventions to enhance time management skills and reduce excessive digital engagement.

Keywords: Tennis athletes, Leisure management, Digital addiction, Social media use, Time management

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INTRODUCTION

Leisure time refers to the period remaining after completing work, education, or daily responsibilities and provides significant opportunities for personal development, social interaction, creative activities, and psychological well-being (Tutar & Turhan, 2023). The quality and utilization of leisure time can directly affect individuals' life satisfaction and overall psychological state. However, with the widespread use of digital technologies, a substantial portion of leisure time is now spent on digital devices such as computers, smartphones, and tablets. This trend has led to an increase in digital addiction and a reduction in engagement with social and physical activities (Alp, 2018; Ergül et al., 2018; Altın et al., 2019; Güler et al., 2020). Digital addiction is defined as the uncontrolled use of digital devices, where individuals cannot limit their internet or gaming time, resulting in negative consequences for daily life, academic, or occupational performance (Akdag et al., 2014; Arslan, 2020). For athletes, leisure management is not only essential for relaxation and stress reduction but also critical for physical performance, motivation, and mental focus (Pirwani et al., 2025). Effective leisure management enables athletes to recover both physically and psychologically, thereby improving training efficiency. On the other hand, digital addiction may hinder athletes' focus during training and negatively affect their performance (Gocer, 2023). In particular, smartphone and digital gaming addiction can prevent athletes from utilizing their leisure time productively and limit social interactions (Namlı, 2025).

The relationship between leisure boredom and digital addiction is also an important topic in the literature. Individuals who are unable to manage their leisure time effectively or experience boredom tend to turn to digital devices to fill their free time (Emir et al., 2025). This behavior, especially among young adults and university students, increases the risk of digital addiction. Additionally, mindfulness levels play a significant role in digital addiction; individuals with higher mindfulness tend to exhibit lower levels of digital addiction and demonstrate more balanced leisure management (Yılmaz, 2025).

Üzgül et al., (2022) investigated digital addiction and loneliness levels among university students and found a positive relationship between digital addiction and loneliness, highlighting that digital addiction is not merely an individual issue but also affects social relationships and psychological well-being. Similarly, Demirel (2022) examined the relationship between digital addiction and leisure management, emphasizing their impact on daily life. Studies indicate that effective leisure management can reduce digital addiction and improve individuals' social, academic, and professional functioning. Moreover, research in the sports context shows that athletes can be affected by digital addiction, which may reduce their performance. In individual sports such as tennis, mental focus and training discipline are critical, making the risks of digital addiction particularly significant (Bozgüney & Alp, 2025; Asan, 2025; Cai et al., 2023). Therefore, examining the relationship between leisure management and digital addiction among tennis athletes is important for enhancing individual performance and supporting psychological well-being.

This study aims to investigate the relationship between leisure management and digital addiction among tennis athletes, providing insights for developing strategies to improve time management skills and mitigate the negative effects of digital addiction. Furthermore, it

contributes to the literature by offering updated evidence on digital addiction and leisure management in the context of athletes.

METHOD

Research Design

This study was conducted using a survey model to examine the relationship between leisure management and digital addiction levels among tennis athletes. The survey model is a quantitative research design that allows for describing the current situation and identifying relationships between variables (büyüköztürk, 2022).

Study Group

The study was conducted with tennis athletes based in Isparta, Turkey. The study group consisted of a total of 219 athletes. The demographic distribution of the participants is as follows: 116 females (53%) and 103 males (47%). Age distribution was 75 participants (34.2%) aged 18–20, 65 participants (29.7%) aged 21–23, 53 participants (24.2%) aged 24–26, and 26 participants (11.9%) aged 27 and above. Regarding athletic experience, 120 participants (54.8%) had 0–3 years of experience, 39 participants (17.8%) had 4–7 years, and 60 participants (27.4%) had 8 years or more.

Data Collection Instruments

The following instruments were used to collect data in this study:

Leisure Management Scale

The Leisure Management Scale, developed by Wang et al. (2011) and adapted into Turkish by Akgül and Karaküçük (2015) with validity and reliability studies conducted, was used in this study. The scale is a five-point Likert-type scale (1 = Strongly Agree, 5 = Strongly Disagree) consisting of 15 items and includes four sub-dimensions: Goal Setting and Method, Leisure Attitude, Planning, and Evaluation. Items 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, and 8 correspond to the Goal Setting and Method sub-dimension; items 10, 11, and 12 correspond to the Leisure Attitude sub-dimension; items 13, 14, and 15 correspond to the Planning sub-dimension; and items 4, 5, and 9 correspond to the Evaluation sub-dimension.

Digital Addiction Scale (DAS)

The Digital Addiction Scale was developed, and its validity and reliability studies were conducted by Kesici and Tunç (2018). This scale consists of 19 items measured on a five-point Likert-type scale. The internal consistency of the scale was calculated as Cronbach's Alpha = 0.874. The test-retest reliability was calculated over a three-week interval and found to be $r = 0.779$ ($p < 0.001$). The scale includes five sub-dimensions: Excessive Use, Relapse, Interference with Life Flow, Mood, and Inability to Quit. In the present study, the reliability of the Digital Addiction Scale was calculated as 0.81.

Additionally, a demographic information form was applied to collect data on participants' gender, age, athletic experience, digital device usage, and preferred social media applications.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected through surveys conducted in Isparta during 2025. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and assured of anonymity, and participation was voluntary. The surveys were completed individually, and incomplete or erroneous responses were checked and excluded as necessary.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS 26.0 software. First, frequency and percentage distributions were calculated for participants' demographic characteristics. Then, the normality of leisure management and digital addiction scores was assessed using skewness and kurtosis values. Differences between groups based on gender, age, athletic experience, and social media application usage were analyzed using t-tests and ANOVA. Additionally, the relationship between leisure management and digital addiction was examined using Pearson correlation analysis. All analyses were conducted based on the total scores of the scales.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with universal ethical principles. Participants provided informed consent, and the data were analyzed anonymously.

RESULTS

Table 1. Demographic Information Form

Variable	Category	f	%
Gender	Female	116	53.0
	Male	103	47.0
Age	18–20	75	34.2
	21–23	65	29.7
	24–26	53	24.2
	27 and above	26	11.9
Years of Athletic Experience	0–3 years	120	54.8
	4–7 years	39	17.8
	8 years and above	60	27.4
Application	Instagram	39	17.8
	Twitter	171	78.1
	TikTok	9	4.1

The study included a total of 219 tennis athletes from Isparta, Turkey. Among the participants, 116 were female (53.0%) and 103 were male (47.0%). The age distribution was as follows: 18–20 years (n = 75, 34.2%), 21–23 years (n = 65, 29.7%), 24–26 years (n = 53, 24.2%), and 27 years and above (n = 26, 11.9%). In terms of athletic experience, 120 participants (54.8%) had 0–3 years, 39 participants (17.8%) had 4–7 years, and 60 participants (27.4%) had 8 years or more. Regarding preferred social media applications, 39 participants (17.8%) used Instagram, 171 participants (78.1%) used Twitter, and 9 participants (4.1%) used TikTok.

Table 2. Normality Statistics

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Leisure Time	219	17	65	0.246	0.526
Digital Addiction	219	27	91	-0.005	-0.525

Based on the normality analyses, the skewness and kurtosis values of the leisure time and digital addiction scores were examined, indicating that the data were suitable for normal distribution. Therefore, parametric statistical tests were preferred in this study.

Table 3. Leisure Management and Digital Addiction Levels by Gender

Variable	Group	n	x	SD	t	p
Leisure Time	Female	116	38.04	7.44	-0.913	0.362
	Male	103	39.04	8.70		
Digital Addiction	Female	116	60.41	13.16	-1.075	0.284
	Male	103	62.33	13.31		

Table 3 presents the leisure management and digital addiction levels of participants based on gender. Independent samples t-tests were conducted to examine potential differences between male and female athletes. The results indicated that there were no statistically significant differences in leisure management scores between females ($x = 38.04$, $SD = 7.44$) and males ($x = 39.04$, $SD = 8.70$), $t(217) = -0.913$, $p = 0.362$. Similarly, no significant differences were found in digital addiction scores between females ($x = 60.41$, $SD = 13.16$) and males ($x = 62.33$, $SD = 13.31$), $t(217) = -1.075$, $p = 0.284$. These findings suggest that gender did not significantly influence either leisure management or digital addiction levels among the tennis athletes in this study.

Table 4. Changes in Leisure Management and Digital Addiction Levels by Age

Variable	Group	n	x	SD	F	p
Leisure Time	18–20	75	36.72	6.94	2.419	0.067
	21–23	65	38.77	7.15		
	24–26	53	40.51	8.89		
	27 and above	26	38.96	10.47		
Digital Addiction	18–20	75	62.16	13.53	0.719	0.542
	21–23	65	61.06	12.14		
	24–26	53	62.06	12.88		
	27 and above	26	57.96	15.77		

Table 4 shows the differences in leisure management and digital addiction levels according to age groups. One-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the potential effects of age. The results indicated that there were no statistically significant differences in leisure management scores among age groups, $F(3, 215) = 2.419$, $p = 0.067$, although the mean scores slightly increased with age. Similarly, no significant differences were found in digital addiction scores among age groups, $F(3, 215) = 0.719$, $p = 0.542$. These findings suggest that age did not have a significant effect on either leisure management or digital addiction levels in the tennis athletes participating in this study.

Table 5. Changes in Leisure Management and Digital Addiction Levels by Years of Athletic Experience

Variable	Group	n	x	SD	F	p
Leisure Time	0–3 years	120	38.88	7.41	1.559	0.213
	4–7 years	39	36.46	7.86		
	8 years and above	60	39.10	9.27		
Digital Addiction	0–3 years	120	60.41	11.97	2.408	0.092
	4–7 years	39	59.31	15.15		
	8 years and above	60	64.42	14.01		

Table 5 presents the leisure management and digital addiction levels of participants according to years of athletic experience. One-way ANOVA was conducted to examine potential differences among the experience groups. The results showed no statistically significant differences in leisure management scores, $F(2, 216) = 1.559$, $p = 0.213$, indicating that years of athletic experience did not significantly affect leisure management. Similarly, digital addiction scores did not differ significantly among the groups, $F(2, 216) = 2.408$, $p = 0.092$, although the mean score was slightly higher for athletes with 8 years or more of experience. These findings suggest that athletic experience does not have a significant impact on either leisure management or digital addiction levels in this sample of tennis athletes.

Table 6. Changes in Leisure Management and Digital Addiction Levels by Social Media Application Usage

Variable	Group	N	x	SD	F	p
Leisure Time	Instagram	39	39.10	9.91	0.246	0.782
	Twitter	171	38.32	7.69		
	TikTok	9	39.67	6.46		
Digital Addiction	Instagram	39	65.44	13.60	2.763	0.065
	Twitter	171	60.21	13.07		
	TikTok	9	64.33	12.24		

Table 6 presents the leisure management and digital addiction levels according to participants' preferred social media applications. One-way ANOVA was conducted to examine differences among Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok users. The results indicated no statistically significant differences in leisure management scores, $F(2, 216) = 0.246$, $p = 0.782$, suggesting that the type of social media application used did not influence leisure management. Regarding digital addiction, although Instagram users had slightly higher mean scores ($X = 65.44$, $SD = 13.60$), the differences among groups were not statistically significant, $F(2, 216) = 2.763$, $p = 0.065$. These findings indicate that social media application preference does not significantly affect either leisure management or digital addiction levels among the tennis athletes in this study.

Table 7. Pearson Correlation Between Leisure Activities and Digital Addiction

Variable	1	2
1. Leisure Activities	1	-0.164*
2. Digital Addiction	-0.164*	1

$P < 0,05$

Table 7 presents the Pearson correlation analysis between leisure activities and digital addiction. The results indicated a significant negative correlation between the two variables (r

= -0.164, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that higher engagement in leisure activities is associated with lower levels of digital addiction among the tennis athletes. In other words, athletes who manage and participate in their leisure time more effectively tend to exhibit lower tendencies toward digital addiction. Although the correlation is modest, it highlights the potential protective role of structured leisure activities against excessive digital device use.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between leisure management and digital addiction levels among tennis athletes. The findings indicated no significant differences based on gender, age, years of athletic experience, or preferred social media application. Gender-based analyses revealed no significant differences in leisure management and digital addiction levels between female and male athletes. This finding is consistent with previous studies; for instance, Emir et al. (2025) and Yılmaz (2025) reported that digital addiction levels are independent of gender.

Age-based analyses also showed no significant differences in leisure management or digital addiction scores. Similarly, analyses based on years of athletic experience revealed no statistically significant differences. This suggests that tennis athletes exhibit similar patterns of digital addiction and leisure management behaviors regardless of age or experience (Üzgü et al., 2022). Analyses regarding social media application usage showed that Instagram users had slightly higher digital addiction scores compared to other platforms, although the differences were not statistically significant. This result supports the idea that the use of digital platforms alone does not determine addiction levels, and that individual habits and behavioral management are more decisive factors (Bozgüney & Akıncı, 2025; Bozgüney & Can, 2023; Kesici & Tunç, 2018; Namlı, 2025).

The most notable finding was the negative correlation between leisure management and digital addiction ($r = -0.164$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that athletes who plan and manage their leisure time effectively tend to be less dependent on digital devices. Similar results have been reported in the literature; Güler et al. (2020) and Akdag et al. (2014) emphasized the reducing effect of leisure activities on digital addiction, and Üzgü et al., (2022) reported a comparable relationship among university students.

These results suggest that interventions aimed at improving athletes' leisure management skills may be effective in reducing digital addiction. Supporting young athletes in time management, social interaction, and psychological well-being can provide significant benefits in terms of both performance and quality of life (Bozgüney & Büyükepekci, 2022; Tutar & Turhan, 2023; Pirwani et al., 2025).

In summary, the findings indicate that leisure management plays a critical role in preventing digital addiction among athletes, whereas gender, age, experience, and social media preferences have limited influence on addiction levels. This underscores the importance of individual awareness and time management strategies within educational and training programs.

Recommendations

To support athletes in managing their leisure time and reducing digital addiction, educational programs should be implemented to enhance planning, prioritization, and overall time

management skills. Sports clubs and coaches should promote awareness initiatives that encourage balanced digital device usage and provide guidance on responsible social media practices, particularly for platforms with higher dependency potential. Interventions should focus on individual habits rather than demographic characteristics, ensuring personalized support. Incorporating group activities and mindfulness practices can foster psychological well-being and strengthen social interactions among athletes. Young athletes should be guided on effective time management strategies to improve both performance and overall quality of life. Additionally, monitoring and advising on social media usage can prevent excessive engagement and mitigate addiction risks. Future research should extend to other sports disciplines and investigate how digital addiction interacts with performance, stress, and motivation to provide a comprehensive understanding of athletes' well-being.

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